

THE EVALUATION OF VOIDS IN THE HIGH INJECTION PRESSURE RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING PROCESS

M. Bodaghi¹, C. Cristóvão², R. Gomes² and N.C.Correia²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, MIT Portugal Program, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Campus FEUP, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

Email: masoud.bodaghi@fe.up.pt, web page: <http://www.up.pt>

² Institute of Mechanical Engineering and Industrial Management

Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, , Campus FEUP, 400 4200-465, Porto, Portugal

Email: ncorreia@inegi.up.pt, web page: <http://www.inegi.pt/>

Keywords: High injection pressure RTM, Void analysis, Carbon fibre–reinforced polymer

ABSTRACT

The recent trend towards the use of unusually high injection pressures (above 1.5 MPa) can significantly reduce RTM cycle time and open new possibilities in part quality: both being very relevant in materializing a significant increase in composite use.

One important issue regarding the study of this new, fast process is the understanding of the possibly inadequate wet-out in a high-speed resin flow inside a fibrous preform, with on impact the mechanical properties of the resulting components through void formation and dry spots. Also, due to the high speed of the process, a better understanding is needed of how manufacturing variables must be coupled with curing conditions in order to obtain high quality processing and adequate process models. To our knowledge there are very few results of experiments which reflect high injection pressure RTM conditions, as the studies that do exist do not yet cover the aforementioned questions of coupled moulding conditions.

Therefore this paper addresses void size distribution in composites produced by high injection resin transfer moulding (HIPRTM) and the effect of mould gap on void content. Void analysis is carried out by microscopy conducted through the thickness of the representative sample. Results of void analysis showed that shows the frequency of occurrence of the void size significantly changes with and without the mould gap. When there is no gap, the HIPRTM delivers the composite part with the lowest frequency of void size of *c.*4 %, showing a significant reduction compared to the gap-closing case. It seems that the gap-closing case promote the appearance of secondary flow phenomena at the top of the preform, which may explain why more voids tend to concentrate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Voids are the major cause of strength reduction leading to early failure of thermoset-based polymer composites[1]. Research has shown how the mechanical properties of composites are drastically degraded as a direct function of void content. This is illustrated in Fig.1 which highlights the effects of voids on interlaminar shear strength(ILSS) of composites [2-8].

Consequently, composite parts that require a very high performance and, thus, lower safety factors (i.e. the lowest possible void content) are today manufactured by autoclave processing. However, this process is not appropriate for mass production of composites due to well known issues of high cycle time and high maintenance and operating costs [9]. In an effort to reduce the manufacturing costs, there is an increasing interest in the use of liquid composite moulding (LCM) as one of the more viable out-of-autoclave technology families. Concurrently however, LCM needs to deliver composite parts with less than 1% voids[10] (or at least 2%) in order to be competitive at the very highest performance level. This has led to the development of high injection pressure resin transfer moulding(HIPRTM) [11].

Similarly to the conventional RTM, in HIPRTM, a fibre preform is placed into a mould cavity. After the mould is closed, air is evacuated from the set. In this case a highly reactive resin is injected at a high pressure (15-20 bars) and subsequently a high compression force (60-100 bars) pushes resin into the preform and establishes the thickness required to reach a desired fibre volume fraction. At the end, the cured part is de-moulded to complete the production cycle. However, this new fast manufacturing process is at an early development stage and has become a prime candidate for process optimization and technical developments; one of which is the understanding of fibre wash-out as highlighted by [12-13]. Due to compacting of a stack of dry fibre at high pressure, a strong fibre displacement is likely and thus resin injection at high pressures will give rise to internal friction and wash-out of individual fibres. To avoid such risks, properties such as the permeability of fibrous media and the understanding of how impregnation at high pressure can occur without fibre movement are key. The former property is related to void size at macro and micro scale, and the latter affects morphology and distribution of voids. In order to understand this issue we report research which, as an initial trial, investigates the influence of the mould gap at high injection pressure (>15 bar) on void size distribution.

Figure 1: The detrimental effects of void on ILSS [2-8].

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation

In this paper two scenarios are considered: (i) the first assumes an injection in a mould that presents a gap (thus increasing permeability) which is closer once the mould is full, (ii) the second scenario assumes that the injection process occurs with a fully closed mould (without a gap). For the gap scenario (scenario 1), the mould is loaded with a stack of 6 fabric layers such that there is a 0.2mm gap between stack and top mould. In the no-gap case (scenario 2), the stack completely filled the mould.

The physical properties of carbon fibre as provided by Hexcel used are summarized in table 1.

Style	Width(mm)	Areal weight(g/m ²)	Weave	Warp(%)	Weft(%)
280T	1000	280	Twill2/2	50	50

Table.1: Physical properties of carbon fibre used for HIPRTM

After the preform is placed in the mould cavity, the mould is closed in a hydraulic press. This is followed by an in-line mixed epoxy injection, allowing high throughput. The properties of the resin system as provided by Sika used are presented in table 2.

Resin system	Resin:BiResinCR120	Hardener:BiResin CH120-3
Viscosity at 25°C(mPas)	900	<10
Density at 25°C(g/ml)	1.13	0.94
Mixing ratio (by weight)	100	30

Table.2: Physical properties of the resin system used for HIPRTM

2.1 Void analysis equipment

In this study, an Olympus PNG3 optical microscope equipped with a CCD camera was used. In order to analyse void sizes, samples were cut along the injection direction and divided into 10 observation regions.

3 RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the frequency of occurrence of the void size and statistical distribution for the samples obtained by high injection pressure with and without gap. As an overall trend, the number of voids decreases as the size of voids increases. In addition to this, a trend in void content reduction with distance to the injection line was also observed. For the gap-closing case, the void size distributions are sharply skewed right, indicating a high number of very small voids at the beginning of the injection process. Results show that there is no definite pattern in the frequency of voids at micro and macro scales, along the length of mould when resin injection is performed at constant thickness (Fig. 2 in gap case). Furthermore, volumes of macro-voids seem to remain fairly constant as the resin flow moves away from the inlet. In contrast, the micro-scale void content dropped as a function of the distance from the inlet. These results suggest that despite reducing the risk of formation of air bubbles in the resin by on-line mixing, some micro air bubbles, which are the primary cause of micro-void formation [14], remain. Comparison of the samples revealed that for the gap-closing case (Fig.3, the left side) the sample contains a higher number of voids along with a wider range of sizes as compared to the case without gap (Fig.3, the right side); the highest frequencies are registered for voids with equivalent diameter less than 50µm. It seems that the mould gap formed between the top mold and the stack could impose higher velocities to the flow channel and higher pressure drops in fibre flow, increasing the probability of air entrapment and subsequently void formation. Meanwhile, when there is no gap, the HIPRTM enable to deliver the composite part with the lowest frequency of occurrence of the void size (*c.*4 %), showing a significant reduction. Another important issue related to quality is the average fibre volume fraction. The results showed that the composite produced without gap and with the subsequent compaction obtained an extra *c.*14% V_f when compared with the gap case. Table 3 summarizes the laminate properties produced with and without gap.

Therefore, the concept of void removal by use of high injection pressure alone in presence of gap may not be sufficient. Since higher fibre volume fraction leads to lower permeability resin may not be able to completely wet the fibre and the formation of dry spots and of high void regions are more probable. This result seems to justify the idea of injection without gap in which external compaction

pressure is increased, not only to eliminate the appearance of secondary flow phenomena but also to allow the first stage injection phase to occur in higher permeability condition.

Property	With gap (0.2mm)	Without gap
Injection pressure(bar)	15	15
External pressure(bar)	2	60
V_f (%)	48	62

Table.3: Laminate properties obtained with and without gap by HIPRTM

Figure 2: Distribution of void size

Figure 3: The Optical microscope of the parts fabricated: with gap (left side) and without gap (right side)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Out of autoclave processes such as RTM, have been widely shown to be cost effective over autoclave processing. However, because of low injection pressure, composite parts produced by RTM have a high void content. Therefore, integration of RTM and high pressure as one potential solution to mitigate void formation was considered. This study investigated whether variant of the RTM process, high injection pressure resin transfer moulding (HIPRTM), is able to produce composite parts with low void content (less than 1%). To do so, effects of the mould gap on frequency of occurrence of classes of void size was investigated. The experimental results showed that having a mould gap, which is a reason for the higher voidage, has a significant effect on the quality of carbon composites. In the sense to avoid dry spots and to have negligible voidage, resin injection without the mould gap in HIPRTM is suggested .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge support of the Portuguese Innovation Agency, within the frame of Project RES2IN, contract N. 171410 of the Program of Incentives to Technological Research & Development. The authors would also like to acknowledge support from the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology, under the research Grant SFRH/BD/51578/2012 and the MIT-Portugal Program.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.W.Beckwith, Manufacturing defects in composite structures, *SAMPE Journal*, 48, 2012, pp.52-53.
- [2] X.Zhang, Y.Duan, X.Zhao, Dichen Li, Effects of Quasi-3D Stacking architecture on Interlaminar Shear Strength and void Content of FRP, *Journal of applied polymer science*, 131, 2014, pp.41076(1-9).
- [3] C.Shin, L.J.Lee, Tackification of Textile Fiber Preforms in Resin Transfer Molding, *Journal of composite materials*, 35, 2001, pp.1954-1981
- [4] M.L.Costa, S. Almeida, M.C.Rezende. The influence of porosity on the interlaminar shear strength of carbon/epoxy and carbon/bismaleimide fabric laminates. *Composites Science and Technology*, 61, 2001, pp.2101–2108.

- [5] C.L.Lee, K.Wei, Resin transfer moulding(RTM) process of a high performance Epoxy resin.II: effects of process variables on the physical, static and dynamic mechanical behaviour, *Polymer engineering and science*, 40, 2000, pp.935-943.
- [6] C.L.Lee, K.Wei, Effect of material and process variables on the performance of resin transfer molded epoxy fabric composites, *Journal of applied polymer science*, 77, 2000, pp.2149-2155.
- [7] A. Y. Zhang, D. H. Li, D. X. Zhang, H. B. Lu, H. Y. Xiao, J.Jia, Qualitative separation of the effect of voids on the static mechanical properties of hydrothermally conditioned carbon/epoxy composites, *eXPRESS polymer letters*, 5, 2011, pp.708-716.
- [8] L.Liu, B.Zhang, Z.Wu, D.Wang, Effects of cure pressure induced voids on the mechanical strength of carbon/epoxy laminates. *Journal of material science and technology*, 21, 2005, pp.87-91.
- [9] R.A.Witik, F.Gaille, R.Teuscher, H.Ringwald, V.Michaud, J.E. Manson, Economic and environmental assessment of alternative production methods for composite aircraft components, *Journal of cleaner production*, 29-30, 2012, pp.91-102.
- [10] G.Gardiner. Out-of-autoclave prepregs: Hype or revolution?. *High-Performance Composites* 2011.
- [11] C.Fais. Lightweight automotive design with HP-RTM. *Reinforced plastics*, 55, 2011, 29-31.
- [12] R.Chaudhari, M.Pick, O.Geiger, D.Schmidt, P.Elsner, F.Henning, Compression RTM - A new process for manufacturing high volume continuous fiber reinforced composites, *5th international CFK-Valley State convention, Stadeum stade, Germany*, June 7-8, 2011.
- [13] F.Gnädinger, M.Karcher, F.Henning, P.Middendorf, Holistic and Consistent Design Process for Hollow Structures Based on Braided Textiles and RTM, *Applied Composite Materials*, 21, 2014, pp.541–556.
- [14] T.S.Lundstrom, Bubble transport through constricted capillary tubes with application to resin transfer molding, *Polymer composites*, 17, 1996, pp.770-779.